

Calibration of the polarization channels for Ceilometers

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Context

Particle depolarization ratio retrieved from ceilometer measurements are used for aerosol layer identification. The particle depolarization ratio is one of the primary parameters that can differentiate major aerosol components but only if the measurements are accurate enough. The accuracy related to the retrieval of particle depolarization ratios is the driving factor for assessing and improving the uncertainties of the depolarization products, particularly in the case of ceilometers with polarization channels, which also require depolarization calibration like in the case of lidar instruments.

In essence, when emitted, linearly polarized light is predominantly backscattered with the same linear polarization, but it becomes partly depolarized upon interaction with atmospheric targets, which are non-spherical and randomly oriented (Mishchenko and Hovenier, 1995). Typically, the collected backscattered signal is detected using polarization-sensitive techniques by separating the signal into two optical paths: the first (parallel or co-polar) containing backscattered light with the original polarization and half of the depolarized light, and the second (cross or cross-polar) containing the remaining depolarized light (Gimmestad, 2008). Alternatively, some systems rely on detecting the total and cross backscattered signals instead (Engelmann et al., 2016).

Calibration

Calibration procedures that could be employed by Ceilometers to optimize the polarization channels:

Polarization channel calibration is tailored to individual lidar and ceilometer systems, although the underlying principles remain largely uniform across most instruments. This calibration process involves evaluating the measured calibration factor and subsequently implementing any required adjustments to minimize instrument-related contributions (Belegante et al., 2018).

To determine the measured calibration factor, one initial method involves employing either the 0-degree calibration or the atmospheric calibration. With this approach, the system's impact on the ultimate lidar depolarization outcomes is evaluated by analyzing a low aerosol altitude range within the lidar signal, where predominantly molecular contributions are assumed. Within this atmospheric

domain, the total volume linear depolarization ratio can be approximated using the established value of the air molecular linear depolarization ratio.

Typically, this process may introduce additional uncertainties, as it necessitates at least two reference points for accurate calibration. Furthermore, a drawback arises from the presence of trace amounts of highly depolarizing aerosols (such as ice crystals) within the presumed clean range, which can easily result in significant errors in depolarization products (Freudenthaler et al., 2009; Freudenthaler, 2016). Alternative calibration techniques include utilizing depolarization optics in the receiver to calibrate the lidar gain ratio (Winker et al., 2007), or employing three lidar signals (cross, parallel, and total) for calibrating depolarization products. The three-lidar signals method involves utilizing two altitude ranges – one with high depolarization and the other with low depolarization load – to derive the calibration constant for the calibration channels.

A dependable approach to calibrating depolarization measurements is through the use of the 45-degree calibration method. This technique involves rotating the depolarization analyzer (comprising Polarizing Beam Splitters and Photomultiplier Tubes) by 45 degrees relative to the laser's polarization plane to ensure uniform light intensity across the cross and parallel channels. By comparing the calibration signals, the ratio between transmitted and reflected signals indicates the influence of optics and electronics within the lidar receiving unit.

A reliable method for calibrating depolarization measurements involves employing the 45-degree calibration technique. This method entails rotating the depolarization analyzer, comprised of the Polarization Separation Unit (PSU) and Photomultiplier Tubes (PMTs), by 45 degrees concerning the laser's polarization plane. This rotation aims to ensure uniform light intensity across both the cross and parallel channels. By comparing the calibration signals, the ratio between transmitted and reflected signals reveals the influence of optics and electronics within the lidar receiving unit.

However, the primary challenge with this calibration method lays in achieving precise accuracy, particularly in executing the 45-degree rotation relative to the PSU's true zero position.

A more reliable approach involves conducting two consecutive measurements by rotating the depolarization analyzer by 45 degrees relative to the default measuring position (David, et al., 2012). This calibration method, known as the "45-degree calibration," determines the calibration constant by utilizing the geometric mean of these two 45-degree measurements. The purpose of employing two measurements is to offset any uncertainties arising from large rotation errors of 45 degrees concerning the initial zero position provided by the Polarization Separation Unit (PSU) (Freudenthaler et al., 2009).

Given that the initial zero position reference holds less significance for the 45-degree calibration, a more generalized approach involves conducting two consecutive measurements with an exact 90-degree difference in the rotation of the depolarization analyzer. This calibration technique, termed the

"delta 90-degree calibration," yields results similar to those obtained from the 45-degree calibration. The 45-degree calibration can be viewed as a specific instance of the delta 90-degree rotation calibration, as the only requirement for this calibration is the 90-degree angle between the two measurements.

The delta 90-degree calibration can be technically executed by employing a mechanical rotator (holder) capable of fixed rotations at delta 90 degrees for the optical components. This device is termed the "delta 90-degree mechanical rotation calibrator." Alternatively, a similar outcome can be achieved by utilizing a half-wave plate (HWP) to precisely rotate the emitted or collected light by delta 90 degrees. An advantage of this approach is that while the mechanical rotator is restricted to placement within the reception unit (either in front of the receiving optics or in front of the Polarization Separation Unit), the HWP module can be positioned at both the emission stage, before and after the emission optics. This device is referred to as the "delta 90-degree HWP calibrator."

Another method for implementing the delta 90-degree calibration involves incorporating an additional linear polarizer capable of fixed rotations at delta 90 degrees. In this scenario, the delta 90-degree rotation is substituted with the presence of the supplementary linear polarizer. Depending on its location within the optical chain (whether in front of the telescope, receiving optics, or the Polarization Separation Unit), this calibration can account for all lidar optics situated after the polarizer, such as the receiving optics, Polarization Separation Unit, and Photomultiplier Tubes (PMTs).

The most straightforward approach is to utilize the Half-Wave Plate (HWP) due to its dual functionality: firstly, it facilitates the initial adjustment of the laser's plane of polarization concerning the Polarization Separation Unit of the analyzer, and secondly, it enables the actual rotation by adjusting the plane of polarization at ± 45 degrees. This solution is particularly advantageous for ceilometer instruments, which typically operate with a single wavelength. Implementing the HWP in front of the entire receiving unit ensures minimal interference with other channels that may be measuring at different wavelengths. This approach enables the calibrator to characterize the entirety of the receiving unit, rather than solely addressing the effects of hardware after the Polarization Separation Unit.

When it comes to the Raymetrics Ceilometer instrument, polarization calibration involves employing an automatic rotation mount and a first-order HWP unit (<https://raymetrics.com/3d-ceilometer/>). This unit can function in an operational mode because the position of the HWP is electronically regulated and synchronized for specific durations.

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Annex 1: Depolarization Calibrator Setup: examples

1. PBS Mechanical rotator

The PBS Mechanical Rotator is employed to rotate a portion of the optics, typically the PBS and the PMTs, to angles of +45 or -45 degrees. This configuration is straightforward to integrate and is ideal for instruments with stable calibration constants, designed to conduct polarization calibration during maintenance or after prolonged periods of operation.

2. WSU Mechanical rotator

This approach builds upon the concept of the "PBS Mechanical Rotator" by extending it to rotate the entire receiving unit of the ceilometer/lidar instrument. To achieve this, it necessitates sizable motors or rotating stages capable of accurately rotating a substantial volume.

3. Filter support

The filter support rotator presents the simplest method for calibrating polarization channels. It is adaptable to any ceilometer unit and can be seamlessly integrated as an additional module into any optical setup. This solution involves a support structure capable of rotation at fixed angles, accommodating either a HWP or a polarizer. However, a limitation is that the calibration procedure necessitates manual intervention by the instrument operator.

4. HWP automatic rotator

The fourth solution integrates an automatic HWP rotator, designed to execute calibration tasks according to a pre-set automated schedule. This innovation significantly enhances operational efficiency by reducing the need for manual intervention, allowing seamless calibration of polarization channels with minimal human oversight.

Annex 2: Theoretical background

To assess the volume linear depolarization ratio we will require the Muller-Stocks matrix formalism.

- we have the subsystems of the lidar

- where

$$M_S = M_R \text{ or } M_T$$

$$I_S = I_R \text{ or } I_T$$

- we have $I_S = \eta_S \cdot M_S \cdot M_0 \cdot F \cdot I_L$
- for the atmospheric contribution we define

$$F = \begin{pmatrix} F_{11} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & F_{22} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -F_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & F_{11} - 2F_{22} \end{pmatrix}$$

- where F_{11} is the backscatter coefficient

$$F = F_{11} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & d & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -d & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 - 2d \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{with} \quad d = \frac{F_{22}}{F_{11}}$$

- we define the volume linear depolarization ratio as

$$\delta = \frac{F_{11} - F_{22}}{F_{11} + F_{22}} = \frac{1 - d}{1 + d} \quad \text{we obtain} \quad d = \frac{1 - \delta}{1 + \delta}$$

All optical elements M_0 can be described by Mueller matrices of diattenuators M_D with retardation M_{ret}

$$M_O(D_O) = M_D M_{ret} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & D_O & 0 & 0 \\ D_O & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & Z_O & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & Z_O \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & c_O & s_O \\ 0 & 0 & -s_O & c_O \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & D_O & 0 & 0 \\ D_O & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & Z_O c_O & Z_O s_O \\ 0 & 0 & -Z_O s_O & Z_O c_O \end{pmatrix}$$

$$T_O = \frac{T_O^p + T_O^s}{2} \quad D_O = \frac{T_O^p - T_O^s}{T_O^p + T_O^s} \quad Z_O = \frac{2\sqrt{T_O^p T_O^s}}{T_O^p + T_O^s} \quad s_O = \sin(\Delta_O) \quad \Delta_O = \varphi_O^p - \varphi_O^s$$

where Δ_O is the retardation (i.e., differential phase shift ϕ of the p and s polarized light components), T_O^p and T_O^s are the optics intensity transmission for parallel (p) and cross (s) linearly polarized light with respect to the plane of incidence of the PBS.

The Mueller matrix of the PBS can be defined as:

$$M_S(D_S) = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & D_S & 0 & 0 \\ D_S & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & Z_S c_S & Z_S s_S \\ 0 & 0 & -Z_S s_S & Z_S c_S \end{pmatrix}$$

The intensity of the detected light for the two components can be defined as

$$I_S = \eta_S T_S T_O F_{11} I_L (G_S + a H_S)$$

with

$$G_S = (1 + D_S D_O) i_E - D_S Z_O s_O v_E$$

$$H_S = D_O (q_E - u_E) + D_S [q_E - [W_O (q_E - u_E) - 2s_O v_E Z_O]]$$

where

$$W_O = 1 - Z_O c_O$$

The first parameter required for testing lidar system performance is the measured calibration factor η^* . We must consider that photodetectors do not have the same quantum efficiency. The measured calibration factor η^* includes the quantum efficiencies of the two photodetectors.

$$\eta^* = \frac{I_R}{I_T} (\pm 45^\circ)$$

For an ideal lidar system, the measured calibration factor should be equal to the actual calibration factor η . However, for real lidar instruments, the measured calibration factor is influenced by all the aforementioned optical parameters. To correct for these contributions, the theoretical correction factor (K) must be determined. This factor is one of the indicators defining the optical performance of a lidar system.

$$\eta = \frac{1}{K} \eta^*$$

The theoretical correction factor can be derived from analytical expressions that incorporate all known depolarization parameters (mentioned above).

$$K = \frac{\eta}{\eta^*} = \frac{\langle A_R(y) | C(\pm 45) | I_{in} \rangle}{\langle A_T(y) | C(\pm 45) | I_{in} \rangle}$$

In the Bra-ket notation, the optical elements of the instrument have been divided into three groups: modules located before the calibrator – I_{in} the calibrator $C(\pm 45)$ and the modules located after the calibrator A_S (Freudenthaler 2016).

The ratio of calibrated signals can be determined using the following relationship:

$$\delta^* = \frac{1}{\eta} \frac{I_R}{I_T}$$

And the linear depolarization ratio can be determined using

$$\delta = \frac{1 - a}{1 + a} = \frac{\delta^*(G_T + H_T) - (G_R + H_R)}{(G_R - H_R) - \delta^*(G_T - H_T)}$$